

On Neutrosophic Semi Alpha Open Sets

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Abstract. In this paper, we presented another concept of neutrosophic open sets called neutrosophic semi- α -open sets and studied their fundamental properties in neutrosophic topological spaces. We also present neutrosophic semi- α -interior and neutrosophic semi- α -closure and study some of their fundamental properties.

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1. Introduction

In 2000, G.B. Navalagi [4] presented the idea of semi- α -open sets in topological spaces. The concept of "neutrosophic set" was first given by F. Smarandache [2,3]. A.A. Salama and S.A. Alblowi [1] presented the concept of neutrosophic topological space (briefly NTS). The objective of this paper is to present the concept of neutrosophic semi- α -open sets and study their fundamental properties in neutrosophic topological spaces. We also present neutrosophic semi- α -interior and neutrosophic semi- α -closure and obtain some of its properties.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$ (or simply $\mathcal{U}$) always mean a neutrosophic topological space. The complement of a neutrosophic open set (briefly N-OS) is called a neutrosophic closed set (briefly N-CS) in $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$. For a neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A}$ in a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$, $Ncl(\mathcal{A})$, $Nint(\mathcal{A})$ and $\mathcal{A}^c$ denote the neutrosophic closure of $\mathcal{A}$, the neutrosophic interior of $\mathcal{A}$ and the neutrosophic complement of $\mathcal{A}$ respectively.

Definition 2.1:

A neutrosophic subset $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$ is said to be:

(i) A neutrosophic pre-open set (briefly NP-OS) [7] if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{A}))$. The complement of a NP-OS is called a neutrosophic pre-closed set (briefly NP-CS) in $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$. The

family of all NP-OS (resp. NP-CS) of $\mathcal{U}$ is denoted by $NPO(\mathcal{U})$ (resp. $NPc(\mathcal{U})$).

(ii) A neutrosophic semi-open set (briefly NS-OS) [6] if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))$. The complement of a NS-OS is called a neutrosophic semi-closed set (briefly NS-CS) in $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$. The family of all NS-OS (resp. NS-CS) of $\mathcal{U}$ is denoted by $NSO(\mathcal{U})$ (resp. $NSC(\mathcal{U})$).

(iii) A neutrosophic α -open set (briefly $N\alpha$ -OS) [5] if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})))$. The complement of a $N\alpha$ -OS is called a neutrosophic α -closed set (briefly $N\alpha$ -CS) in $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$. The family of all $N\alpha$ -OS (resp. $N\alpha$ -CS) of $\mathcal{U}$ is denoted by $N\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$ (resp. $N\alpha C(\mathcal{U})$).

Definition 2.2:

(i) The neutrosophic pre-interior of a neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$ is the union of all NP-OS contained in $\mathcal{A}$ and is denoted by $PNint(\mathcal{A})$ [7].

(ii) The neutrosophic semi-interior of a neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$ is the union of all NS-OS contained in $\mathcal{A}$ and is denoted by $SNint(\mathcal{A})$ [6].

(iii) The neutrosophic α -interior of a neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$ is the union of all $N\alpha$ -OS contained in $\mathcal{A}$ and is denoted by $\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})$ [5].

Definition 2.3:

(i) The neutrosophic pre-closure of a neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$ is the intersection of all NP-CS that contain $\mathcal{A}$ and is denoted by $PNcl(\mathcal{A})$ [7].

(ii) The neutrosophic semi-closure of a neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{T})$ is the

intersection of all NS-CS that contain $\mathcal{A}$ and is denoted by $SNcl(\mathcal{A})$ [6].

(iii) The neutrosophic α -closure of a neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$ is the intersection of all $N\alpha$ -CS that contain $\mathcal{A}$ and is denoted by $\alpha Ncl(\mathcal{A})$ [5].

Proposition 2.4 [5]:

In a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$, then the following statements hold, and the equality of each statement are not true:

- (i) Every N-OS (resp. N-CS) is a $N\alpha$ -OS (resp. $N\alpha$ -CS).
- (ii) Every $N\alpha$ -OS (resp. $N\alpha$ -CS) is a NS-OS (resp. NS-CS).
- (iii) Every $N\alpha$ -OS (resp. $N\alpha$ -CS) is a NP-OS (resp. NP-CS).

Proposition 2.5 [5]:

A neutrosophic subset $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$ is a $N\alpha$ -OS iff $\mathcal{A}$ is a NS-OS and NP-OS.

Lemma 2.6:

- (i) If $\mathcal{K}$ is a N-OS, then $SNcl(\mathcal{K}) = Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{K}))$.
- (ii) If $\mathcal{A}$ is a neutrosophic subset of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$, then $SNint(Ncl(\mathcal{A})) = Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{A})))$.

Proof: This follows directly from the definition 2.1) and proposition (2.4).

3. Neutrosophic Semi- α -Open Sets

In this section, we present and study the neutrosophic semi- α -open sets and some of its properties.

Definition 3.1:

A neutrosophic subset $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$ is called neutrosophic semi- α -open set (briefly NS α -OS) if there exists a $N\alpha$ -OS $\mathcal{H}$ in $\mathcal{U}$ such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq Ncl(\mathcal{H})$ or equivalently if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq Ncl(\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A}))$. The family of all NS α -OS of $\mathcal{U}$ is denoted by NS $\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$.

Definition 3.2:

The complement of NS α -OS is called a neutrosophic semi- α -closed set (briefly NS α -CS). The family of all NS α -CS of $\mathcal{U}$ is denoted by NS $\alpha C(\mathcal{U})$.

Proposition 3.3:

It is evident by definitions that in a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$, the following hold:

- (i) Every N-OS (resp. N-CS) is a NS α -OS (resp. NS α -CS).
- (ii) Every $N\alpha$ -OS (resp. $N\alpha$ -CS) is a NS α -OS (resp. NS α -CS).

The converse of the above proposition need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.4:

Let $\mathcal{U} = \{u\}$, $\mathcal{A} = \{\langle u, 0.5, 0.5, 0.4 \rangle : u \in \mathcal{U}\}$,

$\mathcal{B} = \{\langle u, 0.4, 0.5, 0.8 \rangle : u \in \mathcal{U}\}$, $\mathcal{C} = \{\langle u, 0.5, 0.6, 0.4 \rangle : u \in \mathcal{U}\}$, $\mathcal{D} = \{\langle u, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 \rangle : u \in \mathcal{U}\}$.

Then $T = \{0_N, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D}, 1_N\}$ is a neutrosophic topology on $\mathcal{U}$.

(i) Let $\mathcal{H} = \{\langle u, 0.5, 0.1, 0.3 \rangle : u \in \mathcal{U}\}$, $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{H} \subseteq Ncl(\mathcal{A}) = \langle u, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2 \rangle$, the neutrosophic set $\mathcal{H}$ is a NS α -OS but is not N-OS. It is clear that $\mathcal{H}^c = \{\langle u, 0.5, 0.9, 0.7 \rangle : u \in \mathcal{U}\}$ is a NS α -CS but is not N-CS.

(ii) Let $\mathcal{K} = \{\langle u, 0.5, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle : u \in \mathcal{U}\}$, $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{K} \subseteq Ncl(\mathcal{A}) = \langle u, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2 \rangle$, the neutrosophic set $\mathcal{K}$ is a NS α -OS, $\mathcal{K} \not\subseteq Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{K}))) = Nint(Ncl(\langle u, 0.5, 0.5, 0.4 \rangle)) = Nint(\langle u, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2 \rangle) = \langle u, 0.5, 0.5, 0.4 \rangle$, the neutrosophic set $\mathcal{K}$ is not $N\alpha$ -OS. It is clear that $\mathcal{K}^c = \{\langle u, 0.5, 0.9, 0.8 \rangle : u \in \mathcal{U}\}$ is a NS α -CS but is not $N\alpha$ -CS.

Remark 3.5:

The concepts of NS α -OS and NP-OS are independent, as the following examples shows.

Example 3.6:

In example (3.4), then the neutrosophic set $\mathcal{H} = \{\langle u, 0.5, 0.1, 0.3 \rangle : u \in \mathcal{U}\}$ is a NS α -OS but is not NP-OS, because $\mathcal{H} \not\subseteq Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{H})) = Nint(\langle u, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2 \rangle) = \langle u, 0.5, 0.5, 0.4 \rangle$.

Example 3.7:

Let $\mathcal{U} = \{a, b\}$, $\mathcal{A} = \{\langle 0.4, 0.8, 0.9 \rangle, \langle 0.7, 0.5, 0.3 \rangle\}$, $\mathcal{B} = \{\langle 0.5, 0.8, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.8, 0.4, 0.3 \rangle\}$, $\mathcal{C} = \{\langle 0.4, 0.7, 0.9 \rangle, \langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.4 \rangle\}$, $\mathcal{D} = \{\langle 0.5, 0.7, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.8, 0.4, 0.6 \rangle\}$.

Then $T = \{0_N, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D}, 1_N\}$ is a neutrosophic topology on $\mathcal{U}$.

Then the neutrosophic set $\mathcal{K} = \{\langle 1, 1, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.6 \rangle\}$ is a NP-OS but is not NS α -OS.

Remark 3.8:

- (i) If every N-OS is a N-CS and every nowhere neutrosophic dense set is N-CS in any neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$, then every NS α -OS is a N-OS.
- (ii) If every N-OS is a N-CS in any neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$, then every NS α -OS is a $N\alpha$ -OS.

Remark 3.9:

- (i) It is clear that every NS-OS and NP-OS of any neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$ is a NS α -OS (by proposition (2.5) and proposition (3.3) (ii)).
- (ii) A NS α -OS in any neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$ is a NP-OS if every N-OS of $\mathcal{U}$ is a N-CS (from proposition (2.4) (iii) and remark (3.8) (ii)).

Theorem 3.10:

For any neutrosophic subset $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$, $\mathcal{A} \in NS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$ iff there exists a N-OS $\mathcal{H}$ such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{H}))$.

Proof: Let $\mathcal{A}$ be a $\text{N}\alpha\text{-OS}$. Hence $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})))$, so let $\mathcal{H} = \text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})$, we get $\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})))$. Then there exists a N-OS $\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})$ such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H}))$, where $\mathcal{H} = \text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})$.

Conversely, suppose that there is a N-OS $\mathcal{H}$ such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H}))$.

To prove $\mathcal{A} \in \text{N}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$.

$\mathcal{H} \subseteq \text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})$ (since $\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})$ is the largest N-OS contained in $\mathcal{A}$).

Hence $\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H}) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A}))$, then $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H})) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})))$.

But $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H}))$ (by hypothesis). Then $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})))$.

Therefore, $\mathcal{A} \in \text{N}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$.

Theorem 3.11:

For any neutrosophic subset $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$. The following properties are equivalent:

(i) $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$.

(ii) There exists a N-OS say $\mathcal{H}$ such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H})))$.

(iii) $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))))$.

Proof:

(i) $\Rightarrow$ (ii) Let $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$. Then there exists $\mathcal{K} \in \text{N}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$, such that $\mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\mathcal{K})$. Hence there exists $\mathcal{H}$ N-OS such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{K} \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H}))$ (by theorem (3.10)). Therefore, $\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H}) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\mathcal{K}) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H})))$, implies that $\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{K}) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H})))$. Then $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\mathcal{K}) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H})))$. Therefore, $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H})))$, for some $\mathcal{H}$ N-OS.

(ii) $\Rightarrow$ (iii) Suppose that there exists a N-OS $\mathcal{H}$ such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H})))$. We know that $\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. On the other hand, $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})$ (since $\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})$ is the largest N-OS contained in $\mathcal{A}$). Hence $\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H}) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))$, then $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H})) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})))$, therefore $\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H}))) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))))$.

But $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H})))$ (by hypothesis). Hence $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H}))) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))))$, then $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))))$.

(iii) $\Rightarrow$ (i) Let $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))))$.

To prove $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$. Let $\mathcal{K} = \text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})$; we know that $\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. To prove $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))$.

Since $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))$. Hence, $\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))) = \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))$. But $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))))$ (by hypothesis). Hence, $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow \mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}))$. Hence, there exists a N-OS say $\mathcal{K}$, such that $\mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A})$. On the other hand, $\mathcal{K}$ is a $\text{N}\alpha\text{-OS}$ (since $\mathcal{K}$ is a N-OS). Hence $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$.

Corollary 3.12:

For any neutrosophic subset $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$, the following properties are equivalent:

(i) $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{U})$.

(ii) There exists a N-CS $\mathcal{F}$ such that $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$.

(iii) $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.

Proof:

(i) $\Rightarrow$ (ii) Let $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{U})$, then $\mathcal{A}^c \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$. Hence there is $\mathcal{H}$ N-OS such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A}^c \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H})))$ (by theorem (3.11)). Hence $(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{H}))))^c \subseteq \mathcal{A}^{cc} \subseteq \mathcal{H}^c$,

i.e., $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{H}^c))) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{H}^c$. Let $\mathcal{H}^c = \mathcal{F}$, where $\mathcal{F}$ is a N-CS in $\mathcal{U}$. Then $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some $\mathcal{F}$ N-CS.

(ii) $\Rightarrow$ (iii) Suppose that there exists $\mathcal{F}$ N-CS such that $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, but $\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A})$ is the smallest N-CS containing $\mathcal{A}$. Then $\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, and therefore: $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\mathcal{F}) \Rightarrow \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A}))) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{F})) \Rightarrow \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.

(iii) $\Rightarrow$ (i) Let $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.

To prove $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{U})$, i.e., to prove $\mathcal{A}^c \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$.

Then $\mathcal{A}^c \subseteq (\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A}))))^c =$

$\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}^c))))$, but

$(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A}))))^c =$

$\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}^c))))$.

Hence $\mathcal{A}^c \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}^c))))$, and therefore $\mathcal{A}^c \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$, i.e., $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{U})$.

Proposition 3.13:

The union of any family of $\text{N}\alpha\text{-OS}$ is a $\text{N}\alpha\text{-OS}$.

Proof: Let $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ be a family of $\text{N}\alpha\text{-OS}$ of $\mathcal{U}$.

To prove $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a $\text{N}\alpha\text{-OS}$,

i.e., $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i)))$.

Then $\mathcal{A}_i \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}_i)))$, $\forall i \in \Lambda$.

Since $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}_i) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i)$ and $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \text{Ncl}(\mathcal{A}_i) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i)$ hold for any neutrosophic topology.

We have $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}_i)))$

$\subseteq \text{Nint}(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}_i)))$

$\subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} (\text{Nint}(\mathcal{A}_i))))$

$\subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i)))$.

Hence $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a $\text{N}\alpha\text{-OS}$.

Theorem 3.14:

The union of any family of $\text{NS}\alpha\text{-OS}$ is a $\text{NS}\alpha\text{-OS}$.

Proof: Let $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ be a family of $\text{NS}\alpha\text{-OS}$. To prove $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a $\text{NS}\alpha\text{-OS}$. Since $\mathcal{A}_i \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$. Then there is a $\text{N}\alpha\text{-OS}$ $\mathcal{B}_i$ such that $\mathcal{B}_i \subseteq \mathcal{A}_i \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\mathcal{B}_i)$, $\forall i \in \Lambda$. Hence $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{B}_i \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \text{Ncl}(\mathcal{B}_i) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{B}_i)$.

But $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{B}_i \in \text{N}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$ (by proposition (3.13)).

Hence $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i \in \text{NS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$.

Corollary 3.15:

The intersection of any family of NS α -CS is a NS α -CS.

Proof: This follows directly from the theorem (3.14).

Remark 3.16:

The following diagram shows the relations among the different types of weakly neutrosophic open sets that were studied in this section:

Diagram (3.1)

4. Neutrosophic Semi- α -Interior and Neutrosophic Semi- α -Closure

We present neutrosophic semi- α -interior and neutrosophic semi- α -closure and obtain some of its properties in this section.

Definition 4.1:

The union of all NS α -OS in a neutrosophic topological space (U, T) contained in $\mathcal{A}$ is called neutrosophic semi- α -interior of $\mathcal{A}$ and is denoted by $SaNint(\mathcal{A})$, $SaNint(\mathcal{A}) = \cup\{\mathcal{B} : \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B} \text{ is a NS}\alpha\text{-OS}\}$.

Definition 4.2:

The intersection of all NS α -CS in a neutrosophic topological space (U, T) containing $\mathcal{A}$ is called neutrosophic semi- α -closure of $\mathcal{A}$ and is denoted by $SaNcl(\mathcal{A})$, $SaNcl(\mathcal{A}) = \cap\{\mathcal{B} : \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{B} \text{ is a NS}\alpha\text{-CS}\}$.

Proposition 4.3:

Let $\mathcal{A}$ be any neutrosophic set in a neutrosophic topological space (U, T) , the following properties are true:

- (i) $SaNint(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A}$ iff $\mathcal{A}$ is a NS α -OS.
- (ii) $SaNcl(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A}$ iff $\mathcal{A}$ is a NS α -CS.
- (iii) $SaNint(\mathcal{A})$ is the largest NS α -OS contained in $\mathcal{A}$.

- (iv) $SaNcl(\mathcal{A})$ is the smallest NS α -CS containing $\mathcal{A}$.

Proof: (i), (ii), (iii) and (iv) are obvious.

Proposition 4.4:

Let $\mathcal{A}$ be any neutrosophic set in a neutrosophic topological space (U, T) , the following properties are true:

- (i) $SaNint(1_N - \mathcal{A}) = 1_N - (SaNcl(\mathcal{A}))$,
- (ii) $SaNcl(1_N - \mathcal{A}) = 1_N - (SaNint(\mathcal{A}))$.

Proof: (i) By definition, $SaNcl(\mathcal{A}) = \cap\{\mathcal{B} : \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{B} \text{ is a NS}\alpha\text{-CS}\}$

$$\begin{aligned} 1_N - (SaNcl(\mathcal{A})) &= 1_N - \cap\{\mathcal{B} : \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{B} \text{ is a NS}\alpha\text{-CS}\} \\ &= \cup\{1_N - \mathcal{B} : \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{B} \text{ is a NS}\alpha\text{-CS}\} \\ &= \cup\{\mathcal{H} : \mathcal{H} \subseteq 1_N - \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{H} \text{ is a NS}\alpha\text{-OS}\} \\ &= SA Nint(1_N - \mathcal{A}). \end{aligned}$$

- (ii) The proof is similar to (i).

Theorem 4.5:

Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be two neutrosophic sets in a neutrosophic topological space (U, T) . The following properties hold:

- (i) $SaNint(0_N) = 0_N, SA Nint(1_N) = 1_N$.
- (ii) $SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.
- (iii) $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B} \Rightarrow SA Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SA Nint(\mathcal{B})$.
- (iv) $SaNint(\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B}) \subseteq SA Nint(\mathcal{A}) \cap SA Nint(\mathcal{B})$.
- (v) $SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \cup SA Nint(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq SA Nint(\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B})$.
- (vi) $SaNint(SA Nint(\mathcal{A})) = SA Nint(\mathcal{A})$.

Proof: (i), (ii), (iii), (iv), (v) and (vi) are obvious.

Theorem 4.6:

Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be two neutrosophic sets in a neutrosophic topological space (U, T) . The following properties hold:

- (i) $SaNcl(0_N) = 0_N, SA Ncl(1_N) = 1_N$.
- (ii) $\mathcal{A} \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{A})$.
- (iii) $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B} \Rightarrow SA Ncl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{B})$.
- (iv) $SaNcl(\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B}) \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{A}) \cap SA Ncl(\mathcal{B})$.
- (v) $SaNcl(\mathcal{A}) \cup SA Ncl(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B})$.
- (vi) $SaNcl(SA Ncl(\mathcal{A})) = SA Ncl(\mathcal{A})$.

Proof: (i) and (ii) are evident.

(iii) By part (ii), $\mathcal{B} \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{B})$. Since $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B}$, we have $\mathcal{A} \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{B})$. But $SA Ncl(\mathcal{B})$ is a NS α -CS. Thus $SA Ncl(\mathcal{B})$ is a NS α -CS containing $\mathcal{A}$. Since $SA Ncl(\mathcal{A})$ is the smallest NS α -CS containing $\mathcal{A}$, we have $SA Ncl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{B})$. Hence, $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B} \Rightarrow SA Ncl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{B})$.

(iv) We know that $\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{B}$. Therefore, by part (iii), $SA Ncl(\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B}) \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{A})$ and $SA Ncl(\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B}) \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{B})$.

Hence $SA Ncl(\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B}) \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{A}) \cap SA Ncl(\mathcal{B})$.

(v) Since $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B}$ and $\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B}$, it follows from part (iii) that $SA Ncl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B})$ and $SA Ncl(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B})$.

Hence $SA Ncl(\mathcal{A}) \cup SA Ncl(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq SA Ncl(\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B})$.

(vi) Since $SA Ncl(\mathcal{A})$ is a NS α -CS, we have by proposition (4.3) part (ii), $SA Ncl(SA Ncl(\mathcal{A})) = SA Ncl(\mathcal{A})$.

Proposition 4.7:

For any neutrosophic subset $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space (U, T) , then:

- (i) $Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \alpha Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SaNcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \alpha Ncl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq Ncl(\mathcal{A})$.
- (ii) $Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNint(Nint(\mathcal{A})) = Nint(\mathcal{A})$.
- (iii) $\alpha Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNint(\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})) = \alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})$.
- (iv) $Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A})) = SaNcl(Ncl(\mathcal{A})) = Ncl(\mathcal{A})$.
- (v) $\alpha Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A})) = SaNcl(\alpha Ncl(\mathcal{A})) = \alpha Ncl(\mathcal{A})$.
- (vi) $SaNcl(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A} \cup Nint(Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{A}))))$.
- (vii) $SaNint(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$.
- (viii) $Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq SaNint(SaNcl(\mathcal{A}))$.

Proof: We shall prove only (ii), (iii), (iv), (vii) and (viii).

(ii) To prove $Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNint(Nint(\mathcal{A})) = Nint(\mathcal{A})$. Since $Nint(\mathcal{A})$ is a N-OS, then $Nint(\mathcal{A})$ is a NS α -OS. Hence $Nint(\mathcal{A}) = SaNint(Nint(\mathcal{A}))$ (by proposition (4.3)). Therefore:

$$Nint(\mathcal{A}) = SaNint(Nint(\mathcal{A})) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Since $Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow Nint(Nint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A}))$.

Also, $SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq Nint(\mathcal{A})$. Hence:

$$Nint(\mathcal{A}) = Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Therefore by (1) and (2), we get $Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNint(Nint(\mathcal{A})) = Nint(\mathcal{A})$.

(iii) To prove $\alpha Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNint(\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})) = \alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})$. Since $\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})$ is N α -OS, therefore $\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})$ is NS α -OS. Therefore by proposition (4.3): $\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A}) = SaNint(\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})) \dots \dots \dots (1)$

Now, to prove $\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A}) = \alpha Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A}))$. Since $\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow \alpha Nint(\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq \alpha Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow$

$$\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \alpha Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})).$$

Also, $SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow \alpha Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq \alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})$. Hence:

$$\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A}) = \alpha Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Therefore by (1) and (2), we get $\alpha Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNint(\alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})) = \alpha Nint(\mathcal{A})$.

(iv) To prove $Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A})) = SaNcl(Ncl(\mathcal{A})) = Ncl(\mathcal{A})$. We know that $Ncl(\mathcal{A})$ is a N-CS, so it is NS α -CS. Hence by proposition (4.3), we have:

$$Ncl(\mathcal{A}) = SaNcl(Ncl(\mathcal{A})) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

To prove $Ncl(\mathcal{A}) = Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A}))$.

Since $SaNcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq Ncl(\mathcal{A})$ (by part (i)).

Then $Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq Ncl(Ncl(\mathcal{A})) = Ncl(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow$

$Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq Ncl(\mathcal{A})$. Since $\mathcal{A} \subseteq SaNcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A}))$, then $\mathcal{A} \subseteq Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A}))$. Hence

$$Ncl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq Ncl(Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A}))) = Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A}))$$

$\Rightarrow Ncl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A}))$ and therefore: $Ncl(\mathcal{A}) = Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A})) \dots \dots \dots (2)$

Now, by (1) and (2), we get that $Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A})) = SaNcl(Ncl(\mathcal{A}))$.

Hence $Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A})) = SaNcl(Ncl(\mathcal{A})) = Ncl(\mathcal{A})$.

(vii) To prove $SaNint(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$.

Since $SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \in NS\alpha O(\mathcal{U}) \Rightarrow SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(SaNint(\mathcal{A}))))$

$$= Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})))) \text{ (by part (ii))}.$$

Hence $SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$, also

$SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. Then:

$$SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})))) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

To prove $\mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$ is a NS α -OS contained in $\mathcal{A}$.

It is clear that $\mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq$

$Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$ and also it is clear that

$$Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow Nint(Nint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq$$

$$Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))) \Rightarrow Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq$$

$$Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))) \Rightarrow Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq$$

$$Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))) \text{ and } Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))$$

$$\Rightarrow Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})))) \text{ and } Nint(\mathcal{A})$$

$$\subseteq \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$$

We get $Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$.

Hence $\mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$ is a NS α -OS (by

proposition (4.3)). Also, $\mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$

is contained in $\mathcal{A}$. Then $\mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$

$$\subseteq SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \text{ (since } SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \text{ is the largest NS}\alpha\text{-OS}$$

contained in $\mathcal{A}$). Hence:

$$\mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq SaNint(\mathcal{A}) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

By (1) and (2), $SaNint(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A} \cap Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$.

(viii) To prove that $Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq SaNint(SaNcl(\mathcal{A}))$.

Since $SaNcl(\mathcal{A})$ is a NS α -CS, therefore

$$Nint(Ncl(Nint(Ncl(SaNcl(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq SaNcl(\mathcal{A}) \text{ (by}$$

corollary (3.12)). Hence $Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq$

$$Nint(Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{A}))) \subseteq SaNcl(\mathcal{A}) \text{ (by part (iv))}.$$

Therefore, $SaNint(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{A}))) \subseteq$

$$SaNint(SaNcl(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow$$

$$Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq SaNint(SaNcl(\mathcal{A})) \text{ (by part (ii))}.$$

Theorem 4.8:

For any neutrosophic subset $\mathcal{A}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$. The following properties are equivalent:

- (i) $\mathcal{A} \in NS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$.
- (ii) $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{H})))$, for some N-OS $\mathcal{H}$.
- (iii) $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq SNint(Ncl(\mathcal{H}))$, for some N-OS $\mathcal{H}$.
- (iv) $\mathcal{A} \subseteq SNint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})))$.

Proof:

(i) $\Rightarrow$ (ii) Let $\mathcal{A} \in NS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$, then $\mathcal{A} \subseteq Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$ and $Nint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. Hence $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{H})))$, where $\mathcal{H} = Nint(\mathcal{A})$.

(ii) $\Rightarrow$ (iii) Suppose $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{H})))$, for some N-OS $\mathcal{H}$.

But $SNint(Ncl(\mathcal{H})) = Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{H})))$ (by lemma (2.6)).

Then $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq SNint(Ncl(\mathcal{H}))$, for some N-OS $\mathcal{H}$.

(iii) $\Rightarrow$ (iv) Suppose that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq SNint(Ncl(\mathcal{H}))$, for some N-OS $\mathcal{H}$. Since $\mathcal{H}$ is a N-OS contained in $\mathcal{A}$.

Then $\mathcal{H} \subseteq Nint(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow Ncl(\mathcal{H}) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))$

$\Rightarrow SNint(Ncl(\mathcal{H})) \subseteq SNint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})))$.

But $\mathcal{A} \subseteq SNint(Ncl(\mathcal{H}))$ (by hypothesis), then

$\mathcal{A} \subseteq SNint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})))$.

(iv) $\Rightarrow$ (i) Let $\mathcal{A} \subseteq SNint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A})))$. But

$SNint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))) = Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$

(by lemma (2.6)). Hence $\mathcal{A} \subseteq Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{A}))))$

$\Rightarrow \mathcal{A} \in NS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$.

Corollary 4.9:

For any neutrosophic subset $\mathcal{B}$ of a neutrosophic topological space $(\mathcal{U}, T)$, the following properties are equivalent:

(i) $\mathcal{B} \in NS\alpha C(\mathcal{U})$.

(ii) $Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some $\mathcal{F}$ N-CS.

(iii) $SNcl(Nint(\mathcal{F})) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some $\mathcal{F}$ N-CS.

(iv) $SNcl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{B}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B}$.

Proof:

(i) $\Rightarrow$ (ii) Let $\mathcal{B} \in NS\alpha C(\mathcal{U}) \Rightarrow$

$Nint(Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{B})))) \subseteq \mathcal{B}$ (by corollary (3.12))

and $\mathcal{B} \subseteq Ncl(\mathcal{B})$. Hence we get

$Nint(Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{B})))) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq Ncl(\mathcal{B})$.

Therefore $Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, where $\mathcal{F} = Ncl(\mathcal{B})$.

(ii) $\Rightarrow$ (iii) Let $Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some $\mathcal{F}$ N-CS. But $Nint(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{F}))) = SNcl(Nint(\mathcal{F}))$ (by lemma (2.6)). Hence $SNcl(Nint(\mathcal{F})) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some $\mathcal{F}$ N-CS.

(iii) $\Rightarrow$ (iv) Let $SNcl(Nint(\mathcal{F})) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some $\mathcal{F}$ N-CS. Since $\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ (by hypothesis), hence $Ncl(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq \mathcal{F}$

$\Rightarrow Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{B})) \subseteq Nint(\mathcal{F}) \Rightarrow SNcl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{B})))$

$\subseteq SNcl(Nint(\mathcal{F})) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \Rightarrow SNcl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{B}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B}$.

(iv) $\Rightarrow$ (i) Let $SNcl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{B}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B}$.

But $SNcl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{B}))) = Nint(Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{B}))))$

(by lemma (2.6)). Hence $Nint(Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{B})))) \subseteq$

$\mathcal{B} \Rightarrow \mathcal{B} \in NS\alpha C(\mathcal{U})$.

5. Conclusion

In this work, we have defined new class of neutrosophic open sets called neutrosophic semi- α -open sets and studied their fundamental properties in neutrosophic topological spaces. The neutrosophic semi- α -open sets can be used to derive a new decomposition of neutrosophic continuity, neutrosophic compactness, and neutrosophic connectedness.

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